

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Alkali****FIRST NAME: Dauda****PROGRAM CODE: MTSD****COURSE CODE: ACA 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: Word 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- In academic writing, when the writer reduces multiple causes to one or a few, _____ is said to have occurred.**
 - Superficiality.
 - Anthropomorphism.
 - Plagiarism.
 - Oversimplification.¹**

- In Turabian rule of style, the following are correct about facts of publication except:**
 - It is permissible to translate the city of publication.
 - Give the publisher's name exactly as it appears in the book, even if the name has changed.

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period Four* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 14.

Where there is more than a city of publication, the writer should use only the first.

It is permissible to translate a foreign publisher's name.²

3. **Which of these is not correct about punctuation?**

Indirect questions end with periods.

Semicolons are used in a compound sentence to separate independent clauses that are not connected by a coordinating conjunction.

Exclamation points are usually appropriate for academic writing.³

A writer may use a question mark to indicate doubt or uncertainty.

4. **Using Turabian's bibliography-style citation, which of these is a correct example of a note?**

John Bukar, *The Maniac* (Beijing: Top Press) 2020, p.15.

Bukar, John. *The Maniac* (Beijing: Top Press, 2020) 15.

John Bukar, *The Maniac* (Beijing: Top Press, 2020), 15.⁴

Bukar, John, *The Maniac* (Beijing: Top Press, 2020) p.15.

5. **Which of these is not considered plagiarism?**

When the writer does not provide information about the source because it was gotten from online sources.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 141.

³ Ibid., 177.

⁴ Ibid., 87.

- When the writer quotes what is considered common knowledge and found in many sources.⁵**
- When the writer quotes another person but forgets to cite the source.
- When the writer uses another person's idea in his own words.
6. **The following are secondary legislations in the European Union except:**
- Directives.
- Regulations.
- Treaties.⁶**
- Decisions.
7. **Which of the following is not true about the use of foreign words or phrases in an English text?**
- Personal names retain their accents.
- Italicizing quotations in foreign languages.⁷**
- Italicizing foreign words.
- Placing quotations in foreign languages in quotation marks.
8. **Which of these is a correct example of an in-text citation using the Harvard rule of style?**

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ ACA-401D Coursepack for Period One, Second Edition*. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 10.

⁶ Tim Cooper et al., eds, *European Commission Style Guide English, Seventh Edition* (European Commission), 52.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 31.

(James 2010, p.7).⁸

(James 2010, 7).

(James, 2010) p.7.

(James. 2010, 7)

9. **The use of this/these technique(s) adds interest to a story:**

Analogy.

Irony.

Anecdote.

All of the above.⁹

10. **The following are true about Zotero except:**

Data entered by Zotero are accurate hence need no editing.¹⁰

It collects data about a source.

The writer can use it with different citation styles.

It helps the writer build a library of citations.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ ACA-401D Coursepack for Period One. Second Edition*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

⁸ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period Four*, 8.

⁹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning* (Wilmington: Great Source Education, 1999), 138–139.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition*, 89.

Cooper, Tim, John Fallas, Francis Flaherty, John Jones, Tim Martin, Jonathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend, and Peter Workman, eds. *European Commission Style Guide English. Seventh Edition*. European Commission.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period Four*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. Wilmington: Great Source Education, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.